

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH SKILLS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN MUSIC CLASSES

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Abstract. Traditional educational activities for preschoolers recognize that the teacher tells stories, reads, and memorizes through repetition. But experience shows that children repeat the teacher's story with minor changes, the stories are only interpreted using poor words. This article discusses about the development of speech skills of preschool children in music classes.

Keywords: speech development, mental problem, preschool, music classes, communication skills, etc

Speech development of pre-school children is an important part of the competence approach to education of children defined in the "First Step" State Curriculum. First of all, communicative competence, that is, the formation of the ability to use communication tools in different situations, is defined as the general important competences of a 6-7-year-old child. So, communication competence takes the main place among the game, knowledge and social competence of the students. Therefore, the development of the child's speech and the formation of communication skills is the main task in the content of each educational activity in MTT. Efficiency is high when a child acquires new knowledge based on games and didactic tools. That is, rather than simple reading of fiction, implementation of activities with the use of innovative educational technologies ensures and accelerates the speech development process of each child, thereby helping to improve the quality of education. To do this, it is necessary to develop new technologies for the development of preschool children's speech and actively use them in the process. Forming the speech of preschool children is an important and difficult task. Successfully solving this problem is necessary both for preparing children for the upcoming school and for comfortable communication with others. The pedagogues of our country and the CIS countries have conducted a number of researches on the development of children's speech, in particular, it is possible to meaningfully organize speech development work in MTT using the pedagogical treasure of R. Inog'omova, L. Mominova, V. Gerbova, M. Konin, G. Lyamina, O. Ushakova. The development of preschool children's speech is largely related to the correct solution of the following:

didactic materials for the development of speech include regular speech of parents, educators, fairy tales, poems, songs, stories that are read or told to children;

modern organization of education using didactic materials;

to ensure children's active speech communication in educational games. Today, the educator of the preschool educational organization faces the following difficulties in forming children's speech skills:

identifying and developing the individual abilities of each child;

child activation in educational relations based on cooperation;

creating special game situations with children with hidden speech skills.

Therefore, after reading the story, instead of retelling the story, the game "Find the place of the pictures" that requires the children to put the mixed pictures based on the story on the magnetic board according to their place, encourages the children to be in an active speech situation. In the process of finding pictures according to the sequence of events, they develop not only their speech, but also their attention, observation, and logical thinking. Observing the composition of the story that they are creating activates the students and tries to describe it with new words. This activity protects children from boredom, if it is not possible to retell the story of the whole group, this method involves all children in the work process. Especially when the educator changes his status from the role of the main performer to the level of an observer, it gives children freedom. The pedagogue's encouragement of performing children's behavior paves the way for speech activity.

Taking into account that the main tasks of speech development - enriching and activating vocabulary, forming the grammatical structure of speech, teaching coherent speech are solved in preschool age, special attention should be paid to creative educational technologies. In particular, it is necessary to pay attention to richly equipping the speech development activity center with artistic manuals and didactic materials. It is the educator's responsibility to create a methodical bank consisting of sets of pictures with plots suitable for the topic, sets of toys intended for staging, and printed didactic games aimed at developing all aspects of children's speech. Recognizing that exposure to fiction plays an important role in the development of speech, it is important to organize book corners and "Smart Bookshelf" in groups. Because the pupils get to know new impressions, knowledge, and skills directly with such materials. It is in a favorable environment for the formation of dialogic, emotionally rich speech. As the children's speech and thinking develop with the help of works of art, at the same time they enter into a connected dialogue and begin to express their thoughts. It gives the child pleasure and joy, these feelings are the most powerful tool that stimulates active perception of speech and creates independent speech activity. When we observed this in practice, it became clear that children were active, expressed their thoughts boldly, did not get bored in the process, used new words in their vocabulary, and were eager to learn new information due to their interest. This is the main and necessary requirement for the formation of general important competencies in preparing children for school education in MTT. Taking these into account, it can be concluded that the educational process of speech development in preschool educational organizations and the processes in the activity center of speech development should be carried out using modern technologies. Because the introduction of innovations in the work of the preschool education organization is the most important condition for the improvement and reform of the preschool education system.

The main task of forming a child's personality is the comprehensive and harmonious development of the child. Music education fulfills this task. Musical education for a child is the purposeful formation of a child's personality through the influence of musical art, the formation of interests, needs and an aesthetic attitude to music. It is worth starting to practice with children from the age of four. Canadian scientists say that regular music lessons improve memory and stimulate children's mental development. They were able to obtain the first evidence of the existence of a connection between music lessons and the ability to concentrate. However, despite all the inconveniences that the initial stage of teaching children to play musical instruments brings, previous generations of parents tried to give their

children a musical education. Since music lessons required not only the tireless work and willful efforts of children, but also the endless patience of parents, few of them became professionals, but they still taught everyone, or almost everyone, and considered it necessary. It is known that musical ability is manifested before many other human abilities. The two main indicators of musicality, emotional sensitivity and ear for music, appear in the first months of a child's life. A baby is able to respond emotionally to cheerful or quiet music. He concentrates, calms down, if he hears the sound of ningni. When a happy, dancing tune is heard, his facial expression changes, he comes alive with movement. Studies have shown that a child can distinguish sounds by pitch in the first months of life. This fact is especially evident for those who have become professional musicians.

Mozart showed remarkable abilities at the age of four, he played the organ, the violin, and at the age of five he created his first compositions. The goal of the influence of music on children's education is to introduce them to the whole musical culture. In the development of children's creative activity, music has a great influence on the formation of a child's personality. Music, like any art, is able to influence the comprehensive development of a child's personality, evokes moral and aesthetic experiences, changes the environment, and leads to active thinking. General musical education should meet the basic requirements: be universal, include all children and comprehensively, harmoniously develop all aspects of the formation of the child's personality. Children's musical experience is still very simple, but it can be very diverse. Almost all types of musical activities are available to children on the most basic basis, and the correct formation of education ensures the versatility of their musical, musical and general development of the child's personality. Education of an aesthetic attitude to the surrounding life, development of abilities, emotional empathy, through various feelings and thoughts expressed in the works, the child enters the image, believes and acts in an imaginary situation. The influence of music prompts him to "a wonderful ability to rejoice for others, to care about the fate of someone like his own."

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